

POROSITY INFLUENCE ON THE CHARACTERIZATION OF CMC (C/C-SiC) SPECIMENS

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SUMMARY: The performance of continuous fibre reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) is strongly affected through the open porosity, their development and their influence on the thermo-mechanical load carrying capability.

The C/C-SiC specimens used in this investigation were manufactured at the DLR using the Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) process which is based on the pyrolysis of high carbonaceous precursors and the infiltration of liquid silicon. Quantitative evaluation of the US C-scan mean values show good correlation between open porosity content and attenuation in US C-scan measurements. The influence of porosity on the stress behaviour of the C/C-SiC specimens is corroborated in tensile and bending tests. The acoustic emission measurements conducted during the mechanical tests at room temperature do confirm the influence of porosity in the damage development.

KEYWORDS: US C-scan, ceramic matrix composites, porosity, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMC) are now under development for use in advanced structural aerospace and terrestrial applications that require high temperature damage tolerant materials with low density and non-catastrophic failure modes. Generally, the performance of CMC materials is strongly affected through its constituents: fibre material, fibre architecture, and matrix material, as well as through manufacturing parameters [1, 2]. Open porosity of CMC is one manufacturing defect which influences the thermo-mechanical load carrying capability of CMC materials. One viable way to understand this influence is through analysis of ultrasonic test results correlated to destructive tests.

In the present paper, some results and problems encountered in an ongoing research programme [3] on quality control during manufacturing of CMC, specifically C/C-SiC plates, are presented. The non-destructive inspection (NDI) assessment is based on ultrasonics.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

The C/C-SiC plates were manufactured at the DLR using the Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) process which is based on the pyrolysis of high carbonaceous precursors and the subsequent infiltration of liquid silicon [4, 5]. Commercially available carbon fibre fabrics and a thermosetting resin are used in the resin transfer moulding process (RTM) or autoclave process to obtain Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) as a precursor. The subsequent pyrolysis (C/C-state) is conducted at about 900 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. In this manufacturing step the formation of crack patterns and high open porosity (20 %) in the matrix material are induced. These crack patterns are filled with Si and build a kind of SiC shield around the carbon fibre bundles in the concluding process step and results in the C/C-SiC material, see Fig.1. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) picture shows the characteristic structure of the investigated material and reveals some sources of inhomogenities, e.g. Si-SiC concentration, open porosity, etc. The knowledge about the influence of these inhomogenities on the thermo-mechanical load bearing capability of C/C-SiC are crucial for modelling damage growth and residual life prediction for structures made out of this novel material.

Fig. 1: SEM picture of C/C-SiC (100x)

Specimens were cut from larger C/C-SiC plates (300 x300 mm x 3mm) consisting of HTA or T800 2D-woven fabric layers and thermosetting resin XP-60 or K27, respectively. The specimens had a 0°/90° lay-up and a fibre volume content of $\phi = 60\%$ in the CFRP stage.

Ultrasonic (US) inspection was performed using an immersion scanning technique in the through transmission mode with an apparatus that consisted of a Krautkrämer KB6000, Aerotech Alpha straight-beam US probes with 10 MHz central frequency, a homemade scanning device, a water tank, and a computer.

An example of a US-C-scan measurement is shown in Fig. 2a. The C/C-SiC specimen (300 x 100 x 3mm) has regions with different US signal attenuation, whereby regions with equal US amplitude attenuation have the same darkness. In the gray scale black (0) corresponds to highest attenuation. The plates can have different degree of inhomogeneity depending on the manufacturing history. The source of the porosity, for example, can begin in the precursor stage and continue through the pyrolysis and LSI stage. The density distribution over the plate can also be detected using X-ray. Comparison of global pictures, ie., X-ray and US, have shown [6] that these inspection techniques correlate well. However, the pictures allow only a

Fig. 2a: US C-scan picture of a C/C-SiC specimen

Fig. 2b: Quantitative evaluation of the US C-scan picture (above)

Fig. 2c: Mean porosity distribution over the length of the specimen

rough estimate of the homogeneity distribution. A more objective judgement is only possible after a quantification of the US C-scan pictures. There are various ways to quantify US C-scan results, one viable way is to analyse the global change of the mean amplitude and its standard deviation over the whole specimen. More detailed results can be obtained for example from the mean value distribution of the US C-scan amplitude over the width of the specimen (x) at every point in the length direction (y) of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 2b. Correlation measurements of the porosity, determined using Archimedes principle, on small sections of the specimen after NDI tests have shown that regions with higher US attenuation correspond to zones with higher porosity. The open porosity measurements over the length of the specimen is shown in Fig. 2c.

A global quantitative evaluation of the porosity influence on the US C-scan results for C/C-SiC materials is shown in Fig. 3. The range of the porosity taken into account is high compared to the common values of about $e' = 2.5\%$ in the C/C-SiC stage. After the least mean square approximation there is an exponential behaviour of the US amplitude over the porosity. Through this kind of master chart it is possible to judge the porosity content and its distribution in C/C-SiC structural parts through a US C-scan inspection.

Fig. 3: Influence of porosity e' on US C-scan amplitude

The influence of porosity on the strength of materials is a known phenomena [7]. Fiber reinforced materials are specially sensitive to porosity distributed in the matrix material or in the interphase between fibre and matrix material. C/C-SiC specimens with different porosity content were tested at room temperature under tensile loading or 3 point bending loading. A decrease in strength with growing porosity content can be observed as depicted in Fig. 4. Here the strength values were normalized with the highest tensile strength or 3-point bending strength, respectively.

Fig. 4: Influence of porosity on strength

During some of the tensile tests, acoustic emission measurements were done. The curves of the cumulated acoustic emission counts over the normalized stresses in Fig. 5 show that there is an influence of the porosity on the acoustic emission activity in the specimens. The behaviour for specimens with higher porosity ($e' = 4.28\%$) can be characterized through a higher acoustic emission activity at the beginning of the loading, a middle part with steady growing activity and a final stage with a steep increase of acoustic emission events. Specimens with lower porosity ($e' = 2.77\%$) do show a kind of tableau in the middle part of the loading and a step increase

Fig. 5: Porosity influence on acoustic emission counts over normalized tensile loading stress

short before catastrophic failure. Similar behaviour was also observed with the acoustic emission energy. The smooth increase of cumulative AE counts over the load is an indication of an evenly distributed fine porosity over the specimens with less large discrete pores.

Thermography measurements [6, 8] show that the distribution of pores in the material influences also the thermal diffusivity in the through-thickness direction. In a future work a quantitative correlation between porosity distribution, AE-activity and thermography will be shown.

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of open porosity on the characterization of C/C-SiC materials could be shown. Through the quantitative evaluation of US C-scans it was possible to obtain a correlation between open porosity and US attenuation for the investigated material. Higher porosity means larger US attenuation.

An influence of open porosity on strength of C/C-SiC material at room temperature was evident. A degradation of mechanical tensile and bending strength with higher porosity was demonstrated.

AE- measurements show that there is an influence of the open porosity on the acoustic emission activity of tensile loaded specimens at room temperature. Steady increase of the cumulative number of AE-counts indicates an evenly distributed fine porosity.

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